

D6.2 - Website

prepared for

WP6.2 – Material for dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

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Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
LUWEX	Lunar Water Extraction and Purification Technologies		
AI	Artificial Intelligence		
CE	Concurrent Engineering		
ISRU	In-Situ Resource Utilisation		

1 REPORT SUMMARY / INTRODUCTION

Dissemination and Exploitation of the project progress and results are of vital importance to the success of EU projects. Activities in this direction are undergone in a collaborative manner by the LUXWEX team members.

Both activities are contained within work package 6, which is comprised of different activities for communicating to a diverse group of stakeholders (scientific community, policy makers, industry, the wider public, teachers and students). This report will discuss the development and outcome of the LUXWEX website, which is considered the most important avenue for reaching the largest number of stakeholders.

This task is to create the impact necessary to show that LUXWEX is making an important contribution to European society. Crucial to the success of the website design, is creating a virtual surface where project progress is made visible, including an iconic project identity and logo.

This report will include a description of the conceptual frameworks used for communicating 'project identity' through visual and language means, via website design.

2 WEBSITE DEVELOPMENT AND PROJECT IDENTITY

Developing a clear project identity is important for delivering a product that is recognizable and approachable to the various stakeholders. Project identity goals are the clear communications about project aims and accomplishments. Continuous inputs made on behalf of project partners on the milestone developments within the project, communicated in a timely manner, aim to mobilize scientific dialogue and maximum visibility overall.

Website development and project identity were achieved by the simultaneous development of both. It was an important design driver, to have a visually enticing webpage to capture the essence of the LUXEX project both in a 'light, approachable, and accessible' fashion, as well as one that provided concrete information about project goals, aims and objectives, together with expected outcome and impact. Presenting the project from both sides of the spectrum was conceptualized for allowing the greatest number of stakeholders to have access to the project.

With the use of Midjourney – an artificial intelligence (AI) programme that generates images from textual descriptions, and Photoshop, we created original visuals that aim to comprehensively communicate the project idea, in a more artistic, inspiring and abstract way (see Figure 1).

Figure 2-1: AI generated visuals presenting LUXEX idea

The colours of the images correspond to the LUXEX logo. The other diagrams explaining the project aims, together with the whole website design follow this colour scheme, creating a consistent visual identity.

In the project description, besides diagrammatic graphics presenting the project idea, we also tried avoiding highly technical and specialized language. This way the project is accessible to the larger public.

The address of the website is: luwex.space

3 WEBSITE COMPONENTS

3.1 Homepage

The homepage, which is the landing site for first-come customers provides the main image presenting the artistic idea of the project, together with the project name.

The main visual is meant to capture the project’s essence, presenting the collage of water air-bubble and astronaut sitting on the Moon, drinking water, and looking at the lunar surface (see Figure 2).

The main visual and project name are followed by the three “cards” with three different website sections - news, podcasts and galleries, and a direct link to the most recent news, most recent podcast and most recently added gallery.

The cards are followed by a short project description with the project’s main idea, presenting the consortium partners, and referring to the EU Framework programme. At the footer of the homepage, a logo is featured for each consortium member with a link to their respective websites opening in a new tab. Information regarding project funding by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme is included, as well as the grant agreement number (see Figure 3).

For the easy navigation on the website, at the top of the homepage (and repeated at every other page) there is a menu bar with seven menu items: NEWS, PROJECT, GALLERIES, PODCASTS, PUBLICATIONS, PARTNERS, and CONTACT.

Figure 3-1: LUWEX landing page

WATER ON THE MOON

LUWEX is a project funded under the EU's Horizon Europe framework programme under the lead of the German Aerospace Centre, DLR. LUWEX stands for Lunar Water Extraction. It is focussed on developing technologies to obtain purified water from moon rock.

LUWEX CONSORTIUM PARTNERS

Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt, Germany / LIQUIFER Systems Group, Austria / Technische Universität Braunschweig, Germany / Scanway sp. z o. o., Poland / Wrocław University for Science and Technology, Poland / Thales Alenia Space, Italy

Figure 3-2: LUWEX landing page bottom with partners and reference to EU project grant

3.2 Website Menu Items

Additional sub-pages to the website’s homepage offer additional information on the project and are organized into separate menu items.

3.2.1 News

The News section of the website offers up-to-date news flashes regarding the exciting developments within the project, from participation at conferences, classroom engagements, project partner meetings, to cutting-edge scientific discoveries. The News section aims to illustrate, through its collection of various events and achievements, the dynamic efforts the project attempts to achieve, not only in scientific advancement, but also in applications that could benefit the society at large.

At the time of writing this report, three items have already been included; Virtual Kick-Off Meeting, Press Release, and Concurrent Engineering (CE) study January workshop.

FEBRUARY 12, 2023

Concurrent Engineering (CE) Workshop 1

The LUWEX team met in January 2023 to establish the validation test setup design using the Concurrent Engineering (CE) process. It is a system approach with a focus on optimizing engineering design cycles. It replaces the traditional hierarchical, sequential design-flow by integrating multidisciplinary teams that work collectively and in parallel; often in intense, short studies. [...]

[Detailed Information](#)

NOVEMBER 15, 2022

WATER ON THE MOON

A European science team is advancing the development of water extraction from lunar regolith (surface material).

LUWEX, a project funded under the EU's Horizon Europe framework programme has started with a kick-off meeting under the lead of the German Aerospace Establishment (DLR). LUWEX stands for Lunar Water Extraction and the project is focused on developing technologies to obtain purified water from lunar regolith.

Water is the strategic source of all our life. In space, it is by far the most valuable and most needed resource for human space exploration. It is the key commodity in life support systems as well as for oxygen generation and rocket propellant.

Mission costs are proportional to the amount of mass initially placed in orbit. As we advance deeper into space, the need to support exploration activities with Earth-based resources increases with distance. More than 7.5 kg of propellant and vehicle mass are required to deliver each kilogram of payload to the lunar surface. The collection of available lunar resources is key to a sustainable human presence on the moon or Mars and beyond. Indications for the availability of local raw water ice trapped in the lunar and Martian soil provide the motivation and substantial interest in viable technical solutions for finding, extracting, purifying and utilizing in situ water. Pre-existence research activities regarding lunar water extraction were mostly performed as theoretical system studies, complemented by a few small-scale experiments.

Press release 1

The interdisciplinary LUWEX team coming from Germany, Austria, Poland and Italy is designing and testing a novel water extractor that will be able to process several kilograms of lunar regolith containing enough water ice to support a purification process downstream. The terrestrial demonstration system will operate under a similar low pressure and low temperature environment [...]

[Detailed Information](#)

NOVEMBER 4, 2022

Kick-Off Meeting

The virtual Kick-Off meeting with all LUWEX partners took place 3 November 2022. The first part was open to the public.

[Detailed Information](#)

Figure 3-3: LUWEX website news section

3.2.2 Project

The project is described on a separate page (with no extra sub-pages to click on) and it is divided into Context, Vision/Approach and Objectives, with listed expected outcomes and expected impact.

In the project description we made sure to use language that is less technical and specialized. This was done to ensure that the project is understandable to a wider audience.

We created diagrammatic graphics to present the project idea (see Figure 5) and the expected project outcomes and impact (see Figure 6). The most important, and easy to grasp phrases are put in bold to increase their visibility and ease to read.

Figure 3-4: Diagrams explaining LUWEX main concept

Figure 3-5: Diagrams presenting the timeline of research and innovation of leading-edge ISRU technologies, excellent science for space exploration of the Moon, and supporting the development of the European space sector

3.2.3 Galleries

The galleries section offers up-to-date visual sneak-peak to all activities associated with project development from progression meetings, workshops, participation at conferences, classroom engagements, and to project

partner meetings. The galleries section is a purely image-based Section that relays the spirit of the team and features team members.

At the time of writing this report, one gallery has already been included with the images from the Concurrent Engineering (CE) study that took place in January 2023.

3.2.4 Podcasts

In order to reach to a wide audience, through different means, we will be also running a series of mini-podcasts, developed with interviews of all partners highlighting not only LUXWEX technologies but also present the general context of lunar ISRU. The episodes will be hosted on the LUXWEX website and on Spotify to multiply distribution and access.

3.2.5 Publications

A running list of publications and journal articles will be presented here. At the time of writing the website report, one item has been added to this section, providing access to the LUXWEX press releases.

3.2.6 Partners

The LUXWEX project is comprised of 6 international partners, including universities, research institutions, and companies. On this website sub-page, the expertise of each partner is described, as well as the tasks they will accomplish in the LUXWEX project.

3.2.7 Contact

Contact information including contact person, address, email address and telephone number for each consortium partner is given.

4 CONCLUSION

Dissemination and Exploitation efforts are of critical importance for sharing knowledge of project developments and achievements. The LUXWEX website was conceived as a resource for reaching as many stakeholders as possible, welcoming visitors at a variety of levels, using enticing visuals and different language sets for optimal comprehension.

